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To cite this article: Sari Novieta H., Feliciano Rodney J., Orszagh Erika, Moriceau Nicolas, Benighaus Ludger, Reale Filippo, Dendler-Rafaeld Leonie, Kaszaf Gyula, Szakos David & Frewer Lynn J. (04 Sep 2025): Citizen preferences for risk communication associated with emerging food risks linked to climate change, Journal of Risk Research, DOI: [10.1080/13669877.2025.2553851](https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2025.2553851)

To link to this article: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13669877.2025.2553851>

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Published online: 04 Sep 2025.

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Citizen preferences for risk communication associated with emerging food risks linked to climate change

Novieta H. Sari^a, Rodney J. Feliciano^b, Erika Orszagh^c, Nicolas Moriceau^b, Ludger Benighaus^d, Filippo Reale^e, Leonie Dendler-Rafaeld^e, Gyula Kaszaf^f, David Szakos^f, and Lynn J. Frewer^a

^aCentre for Rural Economy, School of Natural and Environmental Sciences, Newcastle University, Newcastle Upon Tyne, UK; ^bOniris VetAgroBio, INRAE, Secalim (Food safety and microbiology), Nantes, France; ^cDepartment of Digital Food Science, University of Veterinary Medicine, Budapest, Hungary; ^dDialogik, Stuttgart, Germany; ^eGerman Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR), Department Risk Communication, Berlin, Germany; ^fDepartment of Applied Food Science, University of Veterinary Medicine, Budapest, Hungary

ABSTRACT

Climate change is significantly disrupting weather patterns, resulting in negative impacts on the resilience of agrifood systems. One consequence is an increase in emerging food safety risks driven by climate change to humans, animals, and plants resulting from newly identified hazards, which requires policy action to both mitigate, and adapt to, emerging food risks. Although there is evidence that risk perception associated with novel threats may result in heightened citizen concerns, it is not known whether people's concerns about emerging food safety hazards necessitate specific risk communication strategies. A semi-structured interview protocol was developed to understand citizen priorities for risk communication in relation to emerging food safety risks, and to understand if these differed from their preferences and priorities for communication about established risks. Twenty participants from each of the UK, France, Germany, and Hungary were recruited into the study. The results indicated that, although study participants did not distinguish emerging food safety risks specifically from existing food safety risks, they categorised systemic risks (which were potentially associated with climate change drivers) as distinct from acute risks (which had immediately impacted public health and were not categorised as systemic risks, despite the possibility of being caused by climate change). It is concluded that dedicated emerging food safety risk communication is needed to only engage citizens in developing protective behaviours in relation to emerging food safety risks. In addition, it is also relevant to both adaptive and mitigatory actions to reduce the impacts of emerging food safety risks associated with climate change.

ARTICLE HISTORY

Received 25 March 2025
Accepted 14 August 2025

KEYWORDS

Risk communication; climate change; emerging food risks; interview; European countries; citizens

Introduction

Foodborne illness remains a persistent global health threat (EFSA and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control 2024; World Health Organization 2015). Many food-related

CONTACT Lynn J. Frewer Centre for Rural Economy, School of Natural and Environmental Sciences, University of Newcastle, Newcastle Upon Tyne, NE1 7RU, UK

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hazards emerge or are intensified by changing weather patterns associated with climate change (Bolan et al. 2024; Tchonkouang, Onyeaka, and Nkoutchou 2024). An emerging risk within a food supply chain can be defined as one that results ‘...from a newly identified hazard to which a significant exposure may occur, or from an unexpected new or increased significant exposure and/or susceptibility to a known hazard’ (EFSA 2007).

Evidence is required by policymakers and industry stakeholders to improve risk control and mitigation associated with the challenges linked to emerging food safety hazards, and provide the tools for risk analysis, policy development and implementation (Marvin and Bouzembrak 2020; Nordhagen et al. 2022). Emerging risks within the agri-food sector may be driven by (a combination of) socio-economic and biophysical factors (Kendall et al. 2018) and represent a new threat, the re-emergence of an existing threat, the unintended consequences of a planned activity within the supply chain, or emergence of an existing risk identified using new methods (Farkas et al. 2023; Mu et al. 2024).

Emerging risks can be identified in the context of the agri-food supply chain which are specifically linked to climate change. Emerging risks may be a consequence of elevated temperatures and carbon dioxide levels negatively impacting nutrient levels, soil moisture, water availability and other critical performance conditions (Gomez-Zavaglia, Mejuto, and Simal-Gandara 2020). Climate changes may affect crops and crop production as weather systems are affected and act as stressors to plants (Olesen et al. 2011). Increased use of pesticides may be a consequence of climate change as increases in the prevalence of pests are attributed to changes in temperature (Deutsch et al. 2018; Ziska et al. 2018) or pest resistance (Tabashnik, Brévault, and Carrière 2013). Increased occurrence of flooding in agricultural areas may result in runoff of chemical contaminants in natural water courses, increasing risks for foodborne infection, intoxication, antimicrobial resistance, and long-term bioaccumulation of chemicals and heavy metals throughout the food system (Duchenne-Moutien and Neetoo 2021). Foodborne pathogen outbreak risks may increase as pathogen evolution has been altered by climate change, and host–pathogen interactions facilitate the emergence of new pathogenic strains (Singh et al. 2023), compromising long-term food security and natural ecosystem sustainability.

Emerging food safety risks may also be related to the unintended effects of interventions designed to mitigate climate change (e.g. replacement of livestock-based food production systems with alternative proteins may increase health risks associated with ‘ultra-processing’), or adaption to its impacts (e.g. application of genetic technologies to produce plant varieties which are more resistant to heat stress (Ahmad et al. 2021). At the same time, these may invoke societal resistance to their introduction in the agrifood supply chain (Sikora and Rzymiski 2021). Table 1 provides further examples of emerging food risks linked to climate change.

Food safety risk communication is needed to engage with the public on food safety issues (including emerging food safety risks) and their prevention and mitigation, to protect human and environmental health from hazards in food production and consumption (Kasza et al. 2024; Rowe and Frewer 2005; Warren and Lofstedt 2022; WHO/FAO 2016). When an emerging food safety risk is identified, risk management and risk communication strategies need to be developed and implemented and follow principles of proportionality, feasibility, transparency, informativeness, and accessibility with minimal trade restrictions (Frewer 2004; Han et al. 2021; Kasza et al. 2022), and to maintain standards in food and feed safety to protect public health and consumer interests (FSA 2021).

Mitigation strategies need to be communicated to limit and reduce the impacts of emerging food safety risks, if possible and necessary (Feliciano et al. 2022; Gomez-Zavaglia, Mejuto, and Simal-Gandara 2020). Food consumers and supply chain stakeholders should be involved in preventing mitigating emerging and existing food safety risks where behavioural changes are relevant, including in relation to domestic food preparation practices, food production and processing, retail environments and other food choice decisions (EFSA and European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control 2024; Fischer, Frewer, and Nauta 2006; Frewer et al. 2011; Langsrud et al. 2023).

Table 1. Examples of emerging food safety risks linked to climate change.

Emerging food safety risk	Description	References
Methylmercury in marine food chain	Promotion of bioaccumulation of chemical hazards in the marine food chain (e.g. methylmercury), influenced by ocean acidification as CO ₂ emissions in the atmosphere are absorbed by the oceans.	(FAO 2020; Zhang, Dutkiewicz, and Sunderland 2021)
Heavy metals in food crops	Spread of heavy metal chemical hazards due to heavy precipitation as more frequent occurrence and higher volume of rains and can result in (e.g.) spread in chemicals from mining areas or industrial areas.	(FAO 2020; Marrugo-Negrete et al. 2019)
Harmful algal blooms	Algal blooms will increase in waters used for food production and for drinking water, due to higher temperatures and run-offs from agricultural land (e.g. farm inputs, farm waste) initiating eutrophication events.	(FAO 2020; Gobler 2020)
Mycotoxins	Mycotoxins are becoming more common in agricultural production and the food supply chains such as corn, wheat and peanuts.	(Medina et al. 2015; Van Der Fels-Klerx et al. 2012); (FAO 2020; IPCC 2022)
Spread of microbial hazards in food crops	Increased contamination of <i>Escherichia coli</i> O157 and <i>Salmonella</i> spp. due to increased rainfall events that allow their spread from animal reservoirs in farms to crop fields and surfaces.	(Liu, Hofstra, and Franz 2013)
Climate change leading to product deterioration	Extreme weather events such as storms, heatwaves and floods disrupt supply chain logistics and contribute to product deterioration.	(FAO 2020; Misiou and Koutsoumanis 2022; Tchonkouang, Onyeaka, and Nkoutchou 2024)
Toxigenic fungi	Toxigenic fungi are becoming more widespread on farms, affecting croplands, dairy farms, and fisheries.	(FAO 2020; IPCC 2022)

Table 2. Gender of participants by country (participants were also provide with the option of not disclosing this if preferred).

Country		Germany		Hungary		UK		Total
Female (n = 11)	Male (n = 9)	Female (n = 17)	Male (n = 3)	Female (n = 11)	Male (n = 9)	Female (n = 10)	Male (n = 10)	n = 80

The potential human health, environmental, or economic impacts of failing to develop effective food risk communication with consumers has been established in terms of negative health and environmental impacts and economic consequences (Frewer et al. 2016). However, citizen and consumer priorities and preferences for communication about *emerging* food risks may differ from that associated with *existing* risks. Novel or emerging risks may be perceived to be less well understood, uncertain, and uncontrollable, and hence more threatening (Fischhoff et al. 1978; Fox-Glassman and Weber 2016; Slovic 1987, 2016), Hilaire et al. 2022; Jenkins, Harris, and Osman 2021; Kaptan, Fischer, and Frewer 2018). If they have not been fully characterised, emerging food risks may be associated with uncertainty regarding their impact, scale, and geographical range. Communication of uncertainty and what is being done to reduce this by different stakeholders may not be addressed in risk communication (Han et al. 2021), further exacerbating citizen concerns (Brug, Aro, and Richardus 2009; Monaco et al. 2024; Siegrist and Hartmann 2020; WHO/FAO 2016). Food safety risk communication needs to address people's

concerns and priorities, as well as technical issues associated with the hazard and associated risks (Bhardwaj et al. 2023). It is therefore important to determine if there are specific concerns associated with emerging food safety risks which need to be considered in the development of risk communication strategies and practice. *The aim of this research is to identify citizen priorities and preferences regarding emerging food safety risk communication, in particular risks associated with climate change, to enable effective risk communication strategies to be developed.* In this context, the results will contribute to the development and co-design of framework for communicating about emerging food risks.

The following research questions were addressed in this exploratory study:

1. How do consumers perceive emerging and existing food safety risks? Does this vary between countries associated with different food related regulations and socio-cultural contexts?
2. Do people have specific communication preferences and priorities associated with emerging, as opposed to existing, food safety risks?
3. Based on these preferences, should, and which, communication strategies can be developed to deliver risk communication concerning emerging food safety risks?

Methods

A semi-structured interview protocol was developed, based on the existing literature (Appendix 1). Twenty participants were recruited in each of the UK, France, Hungary, and Germany (Table 2). This sample size aligns with qualitative research standards, which consider 5–50 participants to be appropriate, depending on the study's focus and context (Hennink and Kaiser 2022; Wutich, Beresford, and Bernard 2024). Thematic saturation is often achieved within 9–17 interviews in studies with homogenous populations and focused objectives (Hennink and Kaiser 2022; Squire et al. 2024), as was the case in the research presented here. The sample size was determined to capture diverse consumer perspectives across countries, while ensuring thematic saturation within the practical and logistical constraints of our research.

Participants were recruited to ensure a mix of socio-demographic characteristics, including gender and age. (All participants were over 18 years of age). In reporting participant demographics, gender was presented as an important characteristic, because it is a widely recognised factor influencing food purchasing behaviour, risk perception, and health-related decision-making (Bieberstein 2014; Böcker 2002; Leikas et al. 2007). Given the exploratory nature of this study, reporting the most relevant determinant of attitudes, (in this case gender) while ensuring age eligibility supports transparency without overcomplicating demographic reporting, which is appropriate for qualitative studies focused on thematic analysis rather than statistical generalisability (Braun and Clarke 2021). Participants were recruited to represent a mix of socio-demographic characteristics, including gender, age (over 18 years), and socio-economic class.

Each interview lasted between 25 min and 40 min and was electronically recorded and transcribed *verbatim*.

Some initial **warm up or introductory** questions were asked in relation to the main factors asked when making decisions about buying foods, and participants were prompted about their attitudes and knowledge about quality, nutrition, safety, freshness, price, convenience, enjoyment and other relevant factors, in line with research which has shown that consumers have different motives for making food choices across different European contexts (Markovina et al. 2015; Pollard, Steptoe, and Wardle 1998). **Theme 1: Healthiness and sustainability of foods and influences on food choices** considered the extent to which participants considered the healthiness of food when making food choices, (addressing both nutrition and food safety), and sustainability of food, including environmental impact associated with its production. Prompts

included understanding consumer preferences for foods produced using different sustainability measures food miles, seasonality, sustainable production technique, quantity purchased, food reuse, and the need for a circular economy. There is evidence that consumers will prioritise health over sustainability when making food choices (e.g. Ammann et al. 2024; Yue et al. 2024). However, the links between emerging food risks and climate change suggested that introducing both topics would be needed to understand consumers responses to both later in the survey. The issue of **Food safety risks** was now introduced as a superordinate Theme 2 and broken down into subthemes. Participants were, at this stage, provided with a definition of both emerging and existing food safety hazards and the associated risks.

'Food safety hazards can adversely affect the food we eat; they can cause harm such as foodborne illnesses, injuries and allergic reactions or damage to the environment. A food safety risk is the likelihood of a hazard causing harm. For example, if a food contains more of a substance which causes human health problems, it may be more likely to cause human health problems. An emerging food risk is one which resulting from a newly identified hazard, or from an unexpected new or increased significant exposure and/or susceptibility to a known hazard'. Participants were then asked to identify 3 existing and 3 emerging food safety risks to assess whether they clearly distinguished between the 2 risk 'categories'. The next theme, **Theme 2.1: Risk Communication Preferences**, aimed to elicit information about how participants would prefer to receive information about both types of food safety risk, including in an emergency or crisis context. This led to **Theme 2.2: Risk Communication objectives**, which focused on participants prioritisation of the objectives of risk communication about both existing and emerging food safety risks, (prompted by questions focused on their preferences for risk communication related to consideration of human health protection, animal welfare, and/or environmental health protection. In addition, participant preferences for engagement in risk decision-making and communication under conditions of imperfect knowledge or uncertainty was considered (Miles and Frewer 2003), which may be particularly relevant in the context of an emerging food safety risk (Groenen et al. 2025) (Groenen, et al. submitted). **Theme 3: Measuring the success of food safety risk communication** included questions about why, or why not, various issues were considered as appropriate measures to assess whether risk communication has been successful (including reducing negative human health impacts, environmental impacts, economic impacts, for example in relation to employment or reduced waste in the food supply chain, or other measures of success. Finally, questions were asked about their preferences under **Theme 4: Risk communication content and practice** for both existing and emerging risks, (prompted by e.g. what is being done by the authorities to reduce the risk, or actions which could be taken by individual consumers to reduce both types of risks, and how they would like to receive information about mitigation practices).

These themes were designed to investigate consumer attitudes toward both existing and emerging food safety risks, and to capture how consumers think, feel, and behave in response to these risks.

All interviewees were provided with a reward, a small present of locally produced food, or an incentive payment/voucher following their participation in the research. All data were collected between January and May 2024. Ethical approval for the research was provided by Newcastle University Research Ethics Committee, approval number 35563/2023 on 25 September 2023. An informed consent form was signed by each study participant prior to the interviews commencing, and participants were informed that they could withdraw from the research and have their data deleted at any time.

The research followed the standard process for conducting a semi-structured interview. The semi-structured interview protocol was developed in English (see [Annex 1](#)), and translated into French, German and Hungarian by project members. Back translation was applied to assess the accuracy of the translation, and minor adjustments discussed if needed, under circumstances where differences arose between the original English version of the protocol and the back-translated version.

The analyses were conducted using NVivo¹ in UK, France and Hungary, and MAX-QDA² in Germany by the researchers involved in each country, in their respective local languages. A thematic analytical approach was adopted. First, the transcripts were coded, and the codes analysed thematically allow identification of key ideas and procedures. Open coding, in which transcripts were carefully read, was applied to identify cross-cutting themes (Esterberg 2002; Strauss 1987). When new categories no longer emerged, the coding process was finalized as saturation had been reached. This approach has been applied previously in the analysis of qualitative interview data associated with emerging agrifood risks (Hilaire et al. 2022).

Results and discussion³

Participant understanding of emerging food safety risks

Participants in all the countries found it difficult to differentiate between emerging and existing risks, although they expressed concern about future problems associated with climatic changes such as global warming, flooding, and pests such as insects causing problems to food security. They identified potential food safety risks such as outbreaks and antibiotic resistance to result from climate change, although they did not explicitly categorise these as 'emerging' or 'existing'; food safety risks

I don't know if this is emerging... there is a mix up of, you know, hazardous stuff. (UK, F)

I don't have much information about the risks that may arise due to climate change. (HU, F)

Participants experienced difficulty in categorisation which suggests that while climate change is recognised as a pressing concern affecting human and environmental health, including food safety, participants did not distinguish between emerging and existing food risks, and this may not align with how consumers conceptualise food safety in everyday contexts and in the context of climate change. Clear, accessible public communication on emerging food safety risks is needed, as mitigation and adaptation strategies and behaviours are linked to climate change as well as food safety-related actions.

However, participants recognised that climate change was problematic in terms of impacts on human and environmental health, including in relation to food safety. Participants articulated strong concerns about climate change-induced phenomena, such as floods, droughts, and rising temperatures, linking these to reduced food production and broader environmental degradation. These responses reflect a growing awareness of interconnected risks between environmental crises and food security, uncertainty regarding their undetectable presence, and the lack of long-term research on health impacts.

Global warming (impact)... and it is my wife, my son and I who live here. We are seeing the result of the current floods, particularly in the Midlands, Nottinghamshire, and it concerns us greatly ... and that is not healthy. That does not bode good for 2030, and beyond. (UK, M)

Global warming will lead to a reduction in food production. (FR, F)

So, cattle, I think, are causing quite a big problem because of the methane emissions, and that this should be curbed at all costs. So, we're consuming less meat in that respect, for example. but what is certainly disturbing is that we can see that there is clearly also climate change and the problems it is causing. (HU, F)

Climate change-induced phenomena such as floods, droughts, and global warming resonated with participants as pressing and urgent issues which needed to be addressed. Participants linked these events to reduced food production and broader environmental degradation, reflecting a growing awareness of interconnected risks between environmental crises and food security. At the same time, there was concern about the potential drivers of climate change and simultaneous impacts on emerging food safety risks. Microplastics emerged as an emerging threat, linked with a driver of environmental pollution.

Microplastics getting into the sea and the fish eating... (UK F)

Microplastics... sound so alarming because they can be present and difficult to detect. Plus, I think there aren't enough long-term studies yet on what effects it might cause if we consume such food over long period. Perhaps this is what sounds so concerning. (HU, F)

Heavy metals, plastic in fish from the sea. (DE, M)

Participant responses reflected a mix of awareness and uncertainty, recognising microplastics as a potential food safety risk and expressing unease about the lack of long-term research and uncertainty about the human and environmental health impacts of microplastics.

This underscores the importance of addressing public anxieties with robust scientific communication which addresses uncertainties as well as what is being done within scientific research programmes to reduce uncertainty.

Prioritization of food hazards

Some participants described biological and chemical hazards as problematic although did not specifically identify these as emerging food safety risks. Examples included antibiotic resistance, increased pesticide use, GMOs in the food supply chain, and mycotoxins.

Mycotoxins are worth dealing with... climate change is leading to new phenomena that render existing regulations no longer relevant... and I do have the same concerns about the use of chemicals, (such as) citrus fruits being treated with numerous substances, which then remain on the peel, or the additives in processed meats...how they preserve it, and what chemicals they use. (HU, F)

Mycotoxins and antibiotic resistance were recognised to be consequences of climate change. Participants' concerns demonstrated an awareness of complex biological and regulatory challenges, indicating a deeper understanding of the systemic impact of climate change on food safety, emphasising the necessity for current legislation to handle the dynamic problems brought by climate change and modern farming methods. Both mycotoxins and chemical residues were perceived to be emerging dangers that necessitated proactive monitoring, stricter enforcement of safety regulations, and consumer education to reduce their influence on human health. The regulations were perceived to need to identify two issues.

The first is for uncooked and unprepared food and drink. The second is for processed food and drink. They should be labelled accordingly. (UK, M)

Both environmental (e.g. water quality) and socioeconomic concerns were identified as important.

Obviously there are concerns, but there is a whole social order to change. I cannot imagine how microplastics, which have already accumulated, could be cleaned out of anything, even people. So it's already in the circulation And I can't imagine what kind of impact or change would be needed to reduce or eliminate it in the long term. (HU, F)

Participants emphasised the interconnected concerns of food security, (including food safety), affordability, and environmental sustainability. There was evidence that economic pressures were compelling many people, particularly in the United Kingdom and Hungary, to prioritise food cost over food quality, potentially compromising health and safety by choosing cheaper or items close to their expiration dates. At the same time, worries about deforestation, unsustainable farming techniques, and structural failures in food production indicated concerns about climate and environmental issues associated with food production and food security, suggesting participants' support for government intervention, such as subsidies and legislation, in making healthy, safe, and sustainable food accessible and affordable to all, as well as some level of awareness of the link between climate change and food safety problems.

Participant preferences for risk communication and information content

Participants emphasised the importance of clear, accessible information relevant to specific risks such as microplastics and mycotoxins, including potential effects on health and food safety. Participants also expressed a preference for mitigatory, preventive and sustainable solutions, highlighting the importance of addressing 'root cause' of climate change and environmental degradation which were affecting food safety. Proactive measures, such as increasing the sustainability of agricultural practices to minimise environmental harm, were considered as important for mitigating food safety risks associated with climate change. Label and traffic light systems measures were mentioned as potential food safety indicators.

Organisation (e.g., government, producer) wise, they need to inform people that there are risks that they are not..... (For me), there are two main things that are important for me: is it prepared safely? and has the nutritional information. But I wouldn't pay more for it (UK, F)

So, I mean, for example, we do this quite often, to just look at it before we buy, what is in there or some kind of labelling, which there is now... (DE, F)

Geographic differences in concerns

Geographic differences in concerns were also identified. Participants in the United Kingdom and Hungary frequently mentioned concerns about microplastics in the food chain, potentially due to media discussion of these issues, whereas those in France and Germany prioritised systemic climate impacts such as drought, deforestation, and their implications for food production and ecosystems.

Environmental awareness contributes to public understanding of emerging food safety hazards, and it is important to ensure that information is both comprehensible to non-expert audiences and also harmonised across regions, given that climate change and the impacts it has on emerging food safety risks is a transboundary issue, as is the impact of digital media which disseminates information about these issues. At the same time, local concerns need to be addressed as these may be specific to cultural factors linked to specific supply chains or food consumption practices, and what is being done to promote food safety in terms of preventive measures and implementation of long term and sustainable solutions. There was evidence that some food safety risks were perceived as ambiguous, where a lack of clarity or specificity makes it difficult to determine whether hazards are existing or emerging, and whether they are scientifically as problematic in the same way that they are perceived by the public (Costa-Font 2013). In France, participants expressed concern about food safety linked to chemical hazards such as microplastics, water quality issues, preservation or substances used on fruits or additives in processed meats, and pesticide use.

....the use of chemicals, especially pesticides, that are harmful to health. (HU, F)

I am concerned about pesticides, and I look for a declaration they are not using pesticides and using them properly. (FR, F)

One participant specifically pointed out the failure of the government to enforce pesticide regulations, stating,

Less use of pesticide...(France government) failure to enforce pesticide rules. (FR, F)

This statement reflects frustration over the insufficient action taken to control pesticide use, which remains a significant existing concern for food safety in the region. German participants expressed concern about the ecological risks associated with mass-produced food. One participant noted the broader consequences of food production systems, stating,

There is such an incredible lot being... that, you know, this Western standard can be maintained. Every shelf is always packed. Everything of everything is... So much water is being wasted, only for the shelves to be full. And this will have to change in the future.You can't always have everything available. (DE, F)

It's actually the mass production that I'm concerned about, and also the quality implications and the fact that they don't contain the nutrients that they should. And in return they contain a lot of things that are not healthy, if they accumulate of course. (HU, F)

This underscores participants' concerns about the environmental impact of food production systems and the unsustainable practices contributing to food safety risks, such as water wastage and overproduction. Hungarian participants described concerns about emerging food safety risks, while at the same time not identifying these as emerging food safety risk issues. An example was concern about new, unknown chemicals contaminating the food supply, particularly those linked to food imported from outside the EU. Participants were concerned about how the global food supply chain was introducing new, unfamiliar risks.

I think here in Hungary, GMO foods represent a new potential risk, though I can't definitively say whether they are good or bad. (HU, M)

Some concerns were raised about the increasing industrialisation of the food system, and how this is potentially linked to the emergence of new risks.

Yeah, that ever more products are genetically modified or that cultivation... there is no more agriculture but only some... and greenhouses with hydroculture. (DE, F)

Participants were concerned about the growing dominance of industrial farming practices, which are reshaping food production and raising questions about their long-term safety, as well as ambiguities in food safety risk definitions and regulations put in place to protect consumers.

Risk ambiguity and risk definition

Ambiguity was associated with the distinction between existing and emerging risks, compounded by the difficulty participants have in distinguishing between these, and indeed whether some issues represent risks to food safety at all.

GMO food is a new potential risk, but they [the regulators] are unsure whether they are good or bad. (HU, M)

There is potential that the (perceived) ambiguities associated with the risks of climate change is further compounded with the (perceived) ambiguities associated with specific food safety risks, including those which have been introduced to adapt to climate change impacts. An example might be a plant genetically modified to tolerate abiotic stressors resulting from changes in the environment.

Despite the lack of evidence to suggest participants were distinguishing between existing and emerging food risks, the immediate and personal health implications of consuming contaminated food tended to be associated with existing risks, whereas, emerging food risks (e.g. those associated with emerging technologies used in agriculture and ecological threats) were perceived to be systemic risks, reflecting broader concerns about environmental sustainability, food production systems, and their long-term implications for society rather than as personally threatening. An important question arises as to whether this affects people's behaviours in relation to risk mitigation and prevention, and preferences for policy interventions focused on climate change adaptation and mitigation in relation to climate change.

It is important to consider preferences for communication channels about existing and emerging food risks, and it is not clear how these might be differentially viewed by members of society except under crisis conditions. Communication about existing risks was perceived to

be focused on acute, personal health risks, and might be better linked to packaging and information points at point of sale, whereas emerging risks (which are perceived to be systemic) should be communicated digitally or at a more generic level.

Well, ideally of course right where they sell all this, because like this, you are directly being confronted with it. (DE, F)

For me, the emerging one is more in the category of 'Did you know that you should now also pay attention to the fact that I don't know whether such and such packaging can get into your food' - for me, this is such a common thing, and the crisis is that I don't know whether something is affecting hundreds of people somewhere. (HU, M)

What the authorities do, why it is risky, how it can be managed, what it causes, what the consequences are. So, as I said, I'm thinking of a more comprehensive clarification like this in the first place. Obviously, it would be more credible on an official site. (HU, F)

Trust in food risk communicators

Participants had varying perspectives on who were trustworthy players in food safety communication. Public institutions with responsibility for food safety and scientific organisations were often recognised as reputable sources, especially during crises such as foodborne illness outbreaks, which jeopardised human health and socioeconomic security. However, government measures were frequently criticised as ineffective, prompting requests for increased testing and enforcement. Farmers and local producers were perceived positively, being a greater level of transparency regarding production practices and consumer alignment in terms of their values.

I don't know about government half a time. They are lying to other people that this is good for you. And this is good, but they're they are not good for those. (UK, F)

I guess you could always do more. They could test more plants (Betriebe) for example whether they stick to all hygiene, and I don't know which regulations. At the same time, I know that it's probably hard to do in reality with the personnel and such. Still... (DE, F)

So the people who rather do this with passion and who do it on a smaller scale and don't exaggerate. I have more trust towards those because I have got the feeling perhaps, I know them better and because they're less profit-oriented but do this because they want to deliver good quality. And the bigger the corporations, often the more sceptical am I, or the more processed something is after all and the more advertisement they are doing for it. (DE, F)

Well, I would say on TV, but that's not what it's about. They don't announce things like that there anymore, and they're not interested in what people eat...or, well, that would be the thing that would get the widest publicity. But I don't think it's realistic for the government to go along with all that. I don't know, on the internet. Because the shops don't display it either, because it's not in their interest to display where it came from, or at all... I'm telling you; I don't trust the government to allow television to make the general public or society aware of it. So that leaves the internet. (HU, F)

Well, I would think that I would believe the authorities, or if there is university research behind something, a university research institute. (HU, F)

Participants in the United Kingdom, France, and Hungary expressed distrust of their governments and food manufacturers as sources of knowledge about new concerns. However, there is a noticeable contradiction: while government and corporate communication were frequently questioned regarding their motives for communicating about risks, participants continued to identify the need for government officials and scientists to act as important sources of information, perhaps because of their credibility in relation to expertise (Frewer et al. 1996).

The relationship between trust and distrust is frequently based on the perceived distinction between credibility and honesty. Citizens may interact with, and consider, government information, but they may find it difficult to trust it completely. This mismatch occurs when they

perceive the government is not transparent in its decision-making, or is operating to promote its own self-interests, regardless of whether the information is factual or credible. Such scepticism can cause people to overlook crucial insights, not because the information is wrong, but because they have suspicions about the integrity or objective of the source. For example, Hungarians don't trust their government generally, but the Hungarian food safety authority has a good reputation among citizens and is generally viewed as a credible source of information.

I deem what the information they're sending out is of official source. However, I still would not follow it blindly. I would take in... but I don't trust the government ... I would then do other research to look for... another platform, to do a bit of research. Yeah. So, on the one hand ... whatever they (the government) say, I don't trust them wholeheartedly.... (UK, M)

I can say the same thing, let's say the authority is the most trustworthy. if it is information that I have heard from several places, then I would probably be more interested in what exactly it is about and what the risk is. (HU, F)

Effective risk communication plans for mitigation and adaptive behaviours should be provided by, or at least reference, highly include sources, for example scientists and local stakeholders, while at the same time addressing issues about transparency and accountability in governmental and corporate messaging.

General discussion

Climate change and the complexity of global food production methods provide substantial challenges throughout the food supply chain, resulting in interrelated vulnerabilities in food safety systems (Farkas et al. 2023). Systemic risks in food safety are particularly concerning because they cause broad disruptions in production, distribution, and consumption, arise from the highly interrelated nature of modern food systems, and are frequently caused by the accumulation of modest, unrecognised flaws that evolve into crises (Van Der Linden et al. 2025). These risks may be difficult to forecast and control, which increases uncertainty and ambiguity, and complicates risk management, as well as communication to broader society and food supply chain actors.

Although the results presented here are exploratory, there is some evidence that, while not explicitly distinguishing between existing and emerging risks, participants made a distinction between acute food risks (which had a direct impact on health) and systemic risks (linked to climate change and the broader issues associated with emerging food risks). A question arises as to whether participants do not consider emerging food risks to be damaging to human health, and whether this impacts upon personal efforts to adopt mitigatory behaviours to combat climate change. Although we have found little evidence of cross-country differences attributable to national culture or regulation, this may be because of the small sample sizes considered, and future research will address this issue using quantitative measures and representative population samples. However, human responses to climate change and mitigation efforts are heavily impacted by psychological and socio-cultural factors. Van Valkengoed et al. (2022) have noted that individual traits, such as environmental concern, risk perception, and future orientation, play a significant role in shaping pro-environmental actions. They emphasise that cultural and social identity can influence how people perceive and prioritise climate action, with these factors affecting both individual behaviours and support for collective policies (Brick, Bosshard, and Whitmarsh 2021; van der Werff, Steg, and Keizer 2013; Whitmarsh, Poortinga, and Capstick 2021). Similarly, Beattie and McGuire (2020) consider the role of intrinsic motives, such as moral obligation and social norms, as influential in driving climate-related behaviour change. They identify psychological barriers such as cognitive dissonance and denial as acting as barriers to behaviour change, but suggest that these can be overcome by aligning interventions with individuals' values and increasing their sense of efficacy. Framing climate mitigation measures around co-benefits, such as increased health and economic savings, increases engagement. Trust

and inclusivity are also critical in encouraging collective action, particularly in societies with low institutional trust or significant inequality. Participatory approaches that reflect local values can foster acceptance and support sustained climate action and resilience (Dendler et al. 2023). However, it is still unknown which behavioural interventions are most beneficial, when, and why. Interventions that target important determinants of relevant behaviour are more likely to induce pro-environmental behaviour; hence, it is important to identify which interventions influence which factors (Grilli and Curtis 2021; van Valkengoed, Abrahamse, and Steg 2022).

As more emerging risks may emerge under climate change, and as science becomes better able to identify them, there is a need to continually update strategies with new priorities for emerging food safety risk communication. The effectiveness of food safety messaging can also be hindered by a lack of scientific evidence regarding the risks being communicated (Gilman, Henley, and Quinlan 2022), which are being assessed under circumstances where information about their characterisation is incomplete. Given that messages should match consumers' knowledge levels, risk communication needs to be continually updated as more information about an emerging food safety risk and its impacts, becomes understood (EFSA 2018). Further, increasing the relevance of emerging food safety risk to consumers may mean that embedding specific adaptation and mitigation actions which are achievable by consumers into messaging. Risk communication strategies that consider both human behaviour and environmental changes are needed. Climate change intensifies the frequency and severity of food safety hazards, such as contamination, spoilage, and the emergence of new pathogens. To make these risks more relevant to consumers, messaging must include actionable adaptation and mitigation strategies which can be adopted by citizens themselves, allowing people to make educated decisions about their behaviors. However, an overly complicated or negative message may alienate consumers or perpetuate misconceptions, especially as cognitive hurdles such as memory degradation and misinformation may become more elaborated and cumulative over time (Lewandowsky et al. 2012). Instead, risk communication campaigns can leverage motivational elements, such as positive framing, relevant narratives, and co-benefits including health and economic savings, to support behaviour adoption and sustained risk mitigation (Abrahamse 2020; Chambers et al. 2015).

In the context of climate change, consumer behaviour is shaped by internal motivations, cultural norms, and perceptions of trust and efficacy. Risk communication must be aligned with these behavioural drives, particularly for vulnerable populations such as children, pregnant women, and the elderly, who may be more exposed to, or affected by, (emerging) food safety issues. Collaboration among stakeholders is essential, not only for identifying emerging risks but also for integrating these findings into governance, regulation, and public awareness. Risk management frameworks can help to develop a resilient food system by promoting inclusivity and trust, as well as methodically recording emergent hazards *and* their behavioural implications. This approach recognises the social construct of crises, in which unmet stakeholder expectations, such as inadequate responses to foodborne illnesses, can erode public confidence. Proactive, transparent communication based on observed behaviours ensures that both individuals and organisations are better prepared to navigate the evolving landscape of emerging food safety risks in a changing climate.

Limitations

There was some evidence that demographic and cultural differences influenced risk and benefit perception; however, the sample size was too small to allow a comparative assessment of whether these differences were significant. Given that there may be a need for a targeted communication strategy to be developed that focuses on people's concerns about emerging food safety risks as well as technical communication issues, a larger quantitative survey or more extensive qualitative research is needed to provide relevant evidence across nationally representative populations.

An important limitation relates to how existing and emerging food safety risks were defined in this research. Despite the provision of definitions of emerging and existing food risks, participants did not clearly articulate a distinction between these, potentially because such a distinction does not align with how consumers categorise food safety threats in daily life. Rather the distinction between 'acute' and 'systemic' risk suggest a construal effect has occurred, such that immediate risks to personal or human health appear psychologically close, whereas system risks are perceived to be psychologically distant, and, in terms of heuristics, not subjected by participants to elaborative 'in depth' processing, or associated with self-efficacy or the ability to act on these (Braga, Ferreira, and Sherman 2015; Dowd and Artisticco 2016). Thus the framing used here may not have addressed the issue of the potential for heuristics embedded in the language used to influence how the issue of 'existing' and emerging were interpreted by participants.

Future research

An important issue relates to the identification of citizens' perceptions and prioritisation of specific emerging food risks and incorporate this into resource allocation in policy and practice. From this, an important research question relates to how these priorities influence decision-making in relation to agrifood policy, given that we are uncertain as to what extent the public perceives climate change as influencing these risks. For example, understanding citizen preferences for adaptive versus mitigatory actions to reduce the negative impacts of emerging food safety risks requires further investigation, even if these risks are not identified as such.

A question also emerges to whether information provision reduces citizens' reliance on experiential thinking (e.g. affect and social trust) in relation to how they perceive emerging food risks, and prioritise mitigation or adaptation strategies (Epstein 1998). Specifically, research needs to consider the perceived barriers to, and facilitators of, citizens' active searches for information about emerging food risks. This may also relate to the issue of psychological distance, or 'construal' described in the limitations section. We propose that future research might test this by applying alternative framings (e.g. scenario-based examples or through use visual aids) to assess whether framing influences participants responses to their perceived ability to mitigate food safety risks which are perceived to be either 'acute' or 'systematic', or whether other manipulations of heuristic reasoning can be tested in this context.

Although participants recognised the potential impacts of climate change on driving food safety risks, this analysis did not suggest that they distinguished between the two risk 'definitions' (see research question 1). Rather the results suggested that participants made a distinction between acute 'or health-related' food risks and systemic or 'climate-change related' risks. Further, there was evidence that they perceived that they were more motivated and empowered to act to mitigate the former compared to latter. This perception appeared to be a common participant response across the countries included in the research. Some cross-national differences were observed in relation to 'reference' risks as these may have been those to which participants were most exposed within their 'national' information and exposure geographies but this did not distinguish between "existing" and "emerging" risk categories (see research question 2). As a consequence of this lack of distinction, no specific risk communication preferences were identified in relation to existing or emerging food safety risks. This may act as a barrier to developing effective risk communication practices focused on changing behaviours to mitigate risks which are perceived to be 'systemic' and where the risk may not directly and immediately impact an individual's health. Greater research effort is therefore needed regarding the development of effective communication strategies to deliver risk communication concerning emerging food safety risks, particularly those which have a systemic impact, for example in relation to 'one-health' issues (see research question 3).

Conclusion

This research identifies important insights for developing risk communication strategies for emerging food safety risks caused by climate change. Consumers in four European nations were unable to articulate differences between emerging and existing food risks, rather perceiving systemic risks linked to climate change as being distinct, and psychologically "distant" from acute health risks. At the same time, participants stressed the urgency of solving interrelated complex challenges such as environmental deterioration, food safety, and economic impacts. . Clear, actionable , and harmonised information that addresses both local and transboundary risks is needed. .

While systemic risks are perceived broadly, targeted communication could address specific threats such as mycotoxins which are an emerging threat and are a consequence of climate change. Effective risk communication should leverage trusted sources, such as scientists and local producers, while addressing public distrust in government and corporate messages. Integrating clear, actionable strategies for adaptation and mitigation into communication efforts can foster engagement, encourage protective behaviours, and address the interconnected challenges of food safety and climate change.

Notes

1. NVivo Leading Qualitative Data Analysis Software (QDAS) by Lumivero.
2. www.max-qda.com.
3. In the quotes that follow, the participants are identified by nationality (France, FR; Germany, DE; Hungary, HU; and Unted Kingdon, UK); and Gender (Female, F; and Male, M).

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Gabriella Molnár-Füle and Lili Sinkovics for their contribution to organising the interviews and amending the transcripts in Hungary. Ethical approval for the research was provided by Newcastle University Research Ethics Committee, approval number 35563/2023 on 25 September 2023. This research has received funding from the UKRI Horizon Europe grant number 10040684 and European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Actions grant agreement no. 101059813, (HOLiFOOD) (<https://holifoodproject.eu/about/>).

Author contribution statement

Conceptualization: NHS, LJF; methodology: NHS, RJF, EO, NM, FR, LJF; Data Collection: NHS, RJF, EO, NM, LB, LD; data analysis: NHS, RJF, EO, NM, LB, FR, LD, LJF; writing – reporting of results and draft preparation: NHS, RJF, EO, LD, LJF; writing – review and editing: NHS, RJF, EO, GYK, DSZ, FR, LD, LJF; funding acquisition: LJF; supervision: LJF.

Disclosure statement

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the author(s).

Funding

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Actions grant agreement no. 101059813, (HOLiFOOD);UK Research and Innovation grant agree no: 1000035907.

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Annex 1

Warm up question: What are the main factors that you take into consideration when you make decisions about buying food?

Theme 1: Healthiness and sustainability of foods and influences on food choices

- What about the healthiness of the food? Is that something you think about when you buy food? In what ways?
- Is environmental impact something you think about when you buy food? In what ways?

Theme 2: Food Safety Risks (superordinate theme)

We are now going to discuss food safety risks and what you think about these, as well as the best way to communicate about them. Food safety hazards can adversely affect the food we eat; they can cause harm such as foodborne illnesses, injuries and allergic reactions or damage to the environment. A food safety risk is the likelihood of a hazard causing harm. For example, if a food contains more of a substance which causes human health problems, it may be more likely to cause human health problems.

An emerging food risk is one which resulting from a newly identified hazard, or from an unexpected new or increased significant exposure and/or susceptibility to a known hazard.

- Can you name three existing food safety risks about which you are concerned?
- Can you name three emerging food safety risks about which you are concerned?

Theme 2.1: Risk Communication Preferences

- How would you like to receive information about existing food safety risks?
- How would you like to receive information about emerging food risks?

Theme 2.2: Risk Communication objectives.

- What do you think should be the main objective of risk communication about existing food safety risks?
And why?
- What do you think should be the main objective of risk communication about emerging food safety risks?
And why?
- If we do not know everything about the risk, how should we communicate and reduce the food risk?

Theme 3: Measuring the success of food safety risk communication

Should we consider each of the following as measures of successful food safety risk communication, and why (or why not?)

- Human health impacts
- Environmental impacts
- Economic impacts (e.g., in relation to employment or reduced waste in the food supply chain)
- Other (please mention these)

Theme 4: Risk communication content and practice

- What information would you like in terms of risk communication about existing food risks?
- What information would you like in terms of risk communication about emerging food
- Risks?
- Where do you get information about a food safety outbreak?

Interview close

Any other comments or anything you would like to add?

The interviewer thanks the participant and explains the next steps.